

TILES USED IN BUILDING ANCIENT MONUMENTS OF UZBEKISTAN, THEIR TYPES AND COMPOSITION

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Abstract. *In this article, the simple shapes of ceramic coverings are cut out of clay or molded, dried, dipped in a mixture of different colors, and then created by the method of cooking in humdons. Later, it became more complicated and from the second half of Проблемы архитектуры и строительства 2024, №2 11 the 14th century. became the main type.*

Keywords: *memorial, tile, pattern, zoomorphic, raw brick, archaeological, majolica, mosaic, terracotta.*

Introduction

In the architectural heritage of Uzbekistan, the direction of giving luxury to buildings was manifested from the first forms of urban planning. This process, which began in the ancient stone age in the wall paintings in caves and caves, was also perfected in the creation of the first settlements based on human labor. From the IV-II millennia BC, in the early stages of agriculture, the first emblematic patterns appeared in red and red colors, on ceramics. As a result of archeological excavations, the first simple patterns were found on earthenware, and then they were carried out in the interior and exterior styles of buildings. The archaic patterns on the original clay walls were different in different tribes. Broken curves, parallel lines, circles, snake traces, geometric shapes, later became more complex and became patterns in the form of zoomorphic (images of animals), plants, human (anthropomorphic) symbols. In the early Middle Ages (1st-6th centuries), economic, political, and cultural relations were also a place for masters who embodied the signs of culture formed in Central Asia, including the territory of Uzbekistan, Levant, Byzantium, Iran, India, and China. Cooperation with masters The rise of trade relations along the Great Silk Road, the strengthening of international cultural cooperation, also happened in the field of architecture and construction, there is no doubt. In the architecture of this period, the construction of castles was a common practice for every ruler and selfsufficient zamindars. Complexes of such constructions made of pakhsa, raw bricks, and castles, castles and palaces surrounded by thick protective walls were built in Khorezm, Kashkadarya, Zarafshan, Fergana valleys, Choch, and their interior appearance was enhanced in various ways. Along with wall paintings, the first ceramic decorative elements were also used. Ganch, stone, terracotta (baked clay), carved, cast decorative materials are also characteristic of early medieval architectural decorations, and in the 5th-8th centuries, their delicate and complex patterns were identified in Varakhsha, Panjikent. By the beginning of the 9th-13th centuries, the process of the formation of architectural decoration was influenced by the political and economic conditions that occurred in these periods. Arab armies gradually subjugated Central Asia to the caliphate over several centuries. At the end of the 9th century, the ruler of Bukhara, Ismail Somani, created a strong, independent state. From this period, there was development in art, science and culture. Architectural elements of different shapes made of baked brick and ceramic appeared in the buildings [1]. During the rule of the Somonites in the 10th century and the Karakhanids in the 10th-11th centuries, brickwork and carved ornaments reached a high level in architectural decoration. This trend, which started with the decorations of the palace of Termizshahs in Afrosiyab, Surkhandarya, and the brick decorations of Ismail

Somoni's mausoleum, reached a high level in Raboti Malik in Karmana, the minaret in Jarkurgan, Mirsaid Bahrom's mausoleum, Minorai Kalon, Vobkent minaret. The appearance of brick patterns, harmoniously combined with carvings and reliefs, was preserved in the Mag'oki Attori mosque, built in Bukhara in the 12th century. During this period, baked clay - terracotta carved decorative elements began to be widely used. During this period, it is observed that the process of creating terracotta, ceramic decorative elements with air color, turquoise and brown boards started. Such decorative ceramic tiles were found in the Kalon tower of the 12th century. Inscribed ceramic slabs were originally given one or two different colors in the embossed parts. Due to the invasion of Mongols in Central Asia, the use of glazed ceramic or glazed tile in architecture was somewhat delayed. The methods of production of glazed earthenware, formed in the pottery of the Karakhanid period, made it possible to create architectural glazed earthenware decorations during this period. Simple forms of ceramic coverings are cut out of clay or molded, after drying, dipping in a mixture of different colors, creating a colorful glazed ceramic coating by baking in steamers. Later, it became more complicated, and since the second half of the 14th century, glazed tile - architectural ceramic decoration has become the main type of architectural decoration in the territory of Uzbekistan. It was during this period that the tile-based techniques of enamel engraving and printed terracotta (ceramic) full-scale decorative majolica and mosaic appeared and developed rapidly. Masters identified several types of decorative material, which they called tiles. Tile is made of light, porous, flowable silicate clay, which is made by adding a small amount of clay and lime to fine white quartz sand. There is also an opinion that the name Koshin was given because it was invented by the craftsmen of the city of Koshan in present-day Iran. In Movarounnahr, there were tiles made in mortars using crushed glass quartz or quartzites (sand, sandstones). In Khorezm, a mixture of glue (shirach) and natural fine sand was used a lot [2]. Fragile, easy-to-work tiles are used for making Me'morchilik va qurilish muammolari 2024 йил, №2 сон 12 mosaics. The necessary flowers of the pattern are easily sawed in detail and cut with a knife. In the territory of Uzbekistan, in addition to dull colored bricks, tiles with a good glaze are also produced. The ceramic plate is coated with a substance that forms a vitreous layer of light-melting colored glaze. Clear coatings are made of glaze, dull, dull ones are made of colored enamel. Glaze includes materials and oxides that make up the vitreous coating. Lead glazes are made from the chemical addition of silica material to lead oxide obtained by burning metal in air (silica - white sand). But they will not be hard, they will break and cause small cracks (ceka) due to the different coefficient of expansion with the clay. They migrate quickly due to the acid in the air. Lead-free glazes are more durable. They can be used to create different colored tiles. For example, iron oxide gives yellow, red, brown, black and other colors when heated under different conditions and in additives. Copper oxide gives air color, blue and green colors. Sulfuric copper is used in the restoration of ceiling chandeliers as a creator of light effects. Tin oxide, when added to glaze, dulls the clarity of the color (lead-tin, dull glaze or enamel is used to cover the smooth surface of majolica boards). Chromium oxide gives a pure green color, and cobalt salts give a blue color. Instead of vinegar mixtures, natural clays, together with metal salts, were widely used. Additions of iron, calcium, magnesium, sodium, potassium give glaze dark colors. Types of local glazes based on alkali (alkaline plant ash) show a clear, bright, clean and shiny color. The color bouquet of the mysterious patterns looks different depending on the viewing angle and the intensity of each color depending on the change of light. These factors determine the individual skills of each master tiler and tiler [3]. In Central Asia, especially Uzbekistan, the basis of architectural decorative coverings are square, rectangular, hexagonal

ceramic tiles, and cut brick surfaces. They are covered with ganch mixtures on the surface of the structure. Muqarnas are baked in special forms and glazed to ceramics (pottery). There are also muqarnas elements cast from ganch, which are then covered with majolica boards. There are different types of majolica glazed tiles, such as ceramic tiles with different colored glazes, tiles with patterns on the surface, majolica tiles with black borders and enamel patterns or different colors with carved borders, and gilded tiles. Each glaze has its own firing point, at which point the color comes out clear and bright. Therefore, each color is cooked separately. Patterns printed on majolica boards of different colors are not baked at the same temperature. A board for each color is cooked separately in the oven. Therefore, it is convenient to type the coverings in a mosaic method. It is possible to make each pattern in different sizes, to achieve clean and bright colors. However, coating with majolica boards requires relatively little work, and the main thing is that it allows to increase the gloss of colors, free placement of patterns, and the artistry of decoration. An architectural decorative coating that does not blend into one another, it is the cutting of tiles to create a mosaic (koshinburush). A piece of tile cut into pattern lines on paper or a flat surface is sorted by color and ganch is poured over it. In the same way, pieces of tile are picked up and hardened with ganch on the surface of curved, arc-shaped surfaces drawn on the roof. A certain size piece of a tile mosaic hardened with a hammer is installed in a designated place on the wall. A welldefined general pattern will be imperceptible. Tilers used the khataba method when installing common tiles on the wall surface, that is, they leave an air gap between the wall surface and the tile - ganch coating. In this way, the grout that holds the tile hardens quickly, and the condensation in the air between the wall and the tile coating makes it easier to remove moisture, thus protecting the tile from spills. Unique schools of architectural decoration of Khorezm, Samarkand, Bukhara were formed in medieval tiling. Kashkadarya and Fergana schools also functioned independently. The representatives of these schools were not left behind by skilled foreign masters brought in during the Timurid period. Each of these schools has left its mark on the art of architectural decoration in Uzbekistan [4]. The first Khorezm pottery was discovered in the 14th century in the tombstone of Najmuddin Kubra in Old Urganch (20-40s of the 14th century), in the mausoleum of Khoja Allouddin (Khiva), and in the mausoleum of Mazlum Khan Suluv. The patterned majolica tiles of various shapes with delicate Islamic flowers are done with great skill. Dark blue, inky ground is coordinated with white, yellow, airy flowers, Arabic inscriptions, ornaments on four sides. Khoja Olovuddin's tombstone is an example of majolica decoration that has no equal of its time. During the period when Khorezm masters were perfecting the majolica decoration, Bukhara and Samarkand masters brought glaze to the traditional carved ceramic boards, bricks, elements (terracotta) and continued the tradition of porcelain tiles formed before the Mongol invasion and brought cast porcelain architectural decoration to a perfect level. This direction was preserved until the Timurid period. In the 30s-70s of the 14th century, the mausoleums of Qusam ibn Abbas, Khoja Ahmad, 1360, the mausoleum of Turkan Aqo and Tughluq Tekin, and the mausoleum of Buyonkulikhon in Bukhara, built in the Shahizinda complex of Samarkand, clearly showed the possibilities of this direction. In the tomb of Qusam ibn Abbas (XIIXIV centuries), several types of covering of carved terracotta with cast glazes have been identified. The designs on the majolica tiles are embossed in a kundal style, and the geometric shapes are carved with glazed ceramic. The colors of the patterns in the mausoleum cave are different, and the flowers are similar to the patterns of the XI-XII centuries. Glazed bricks were made along with cast glazed elements with relief patterns. Arabic inscriptions with carvings are very skillful, an example of which can be seen in the mausoleum of Khoja Ahmed (XIV century).

By the time of the Timurids, high and diverse types, methods, and forms of architectural ceramics appeared. Patterned majolica is not only a set of boards that cover vertical surfaces: in addition to nimustuns, cornices, muqarnas, signs, the complex geometric shapes of arches, bagals, domes, domes under the dome are also covered with Проблемы архитектуры и строительства 2024, №2 13 boards of different shapes. In the period of Timurids, together with majolica, carved glazed tiles and cut tiles were used together. The practice of applying gold to the surface of printed, engraved, and embossed lacquered boards also appeared. The mausoleum of Tughlu Tekin (1375-1376) in Shahizinda, where the patterns on the top and bottom of the glaze are shown on the six-sided majolica board, was skillfully used. Koshinburush, which was widely used in the later periods, was also used in the architectural decoration of the Timurid period. More than 40 monuments of the historical-architectural complex of Shahizin in Samarkand embody all types of the art of tiling in the heritage of Central Asian architecture and are considered the masterpieces of architectural decoration of the Timurid period. Various methods of ceramic coverings with an as-yet-unrevealed pattern of architectural ceramics have also been identified in archaeological excavations. Such ceramic coverings were found in the remains of the madrasa built in 1066 by ruler Tamgoch Bugrokhon from the Karakhanid dynasty. In the remains of the main entrance gate of the madrasa, there are also terracotta carvings in the same airy color. The types of carved ceramics with intricate designs and decorated with different glaze colors were used for the mausoleums of Khwaja Ahmad and 1361, which were built at the place where the first western road of the Shahizinda complex was completed. Glazed brick mosaics, carved tiles, glazed ceramic tiles, engraving fine lines of Arabic inscriptions on the carved clay - all these indicate the high level of artistic possibilities of the glazed ceramic material used in the architectural decoration of the Timurid period. Examples of tiling decorations from majolica to very fine cut tiles in the architectural decoration of the Timurid era are available in the mausoleums of the Shahizinda complex built during the Timurid era. These tile coverings determined the main directions of the further development of tiling in the architectural decoration of Central Asia [5]. Various covering decorations produced on the basis of architectural ceramics - ceramics are known in all regions of the world where pottery is spread, and are even called by the names of some countries. For example, porcelain made by Chin (Chinese) potters was brought to Western countries from ancient times through the Great Silk Road. Porcelain vases (porcelain vases) made in China were very delicate and sonorous. Even the box in one of the gardens built by Ulugbek was covered with porcelain. Porcelain shapes were made from white clay, with a certain amount of crushed stone powder (feldspar) added to the clay, which was called "kaolin" after the place where high-quality soil for the production of porcelain was found in the VI-VII centuries, and baked at a very high level of heat. Ceramics (porcelain) obtained in this way were leaky and brittle. In the 7th and 8th centuries, porcelain was painted with colored images and patterns (colored varnish) and then baked in a furnace. Of course, there was an attempt to produce such porcelain products in Central Asia. But the local materials here (clay, ganch) allowed to create monand ceramics of only high level porcelain. The use of angob instead of lacquer ensured that the glaze of the ceramic was clear and elegantly polished. That is, lead and tin glazes are processed by making the white color contained in the alkali liquid and applying it to ceramic, terracotta before glazing. Because the angob is white, when the main glaze (paints) are applied to the surface of the tiles and they are baked again, they are resistant to any cold and moisture, they do not move, and the colors come out clean. Some experts say that the angob, angobling process, which originated in the ancient Greek pottery art of Western Europe, was supplanted by Middle

Eastern potters in the 9th century and replaced by angob, enamel, and vitreous glaze. There is also an opinion that the rough and uneven places are covered with white or colored liquid clay before firing, that is, the liquid and thin layer of white clay forms a smooth layer during the firing of the clay, which is called angob in French. The development of this direction has given rise to lacquer coatings, glaze, enamel. The word glaze (glaze) comes from the German word "glas" - "glass", and it refers to the vitreous layer on top of the ceramic. Glazed ceramic gives a decorative look while maintaining an atmospheric effect. Glaze (glaze) is a vitreous layer formed by adding oxide (salt) of sodium, potassium, magnesium, silicon, aluminum and other metals. Stiff glazes are glass (quartz - white sand) glazes, which are called enamel in Europe, that is, heavy metal oxides are mixed. About the preparation of such secrets, Abu Rayhan Beruni also writes about one of the ancient methods in his book "Mineralogy": "Enamel baked by taking feldspar and rock crystal in a certain proportion and adding tin salt and soda (soda) comes out colorful like precious stones. It depends on the added mineral dyes. For example: lead oxide (suric) emits a yellow color, copper oxide - green, burnt gold, dark red, and cerdalic (precious stone) powder emits a purple color. Eastern masters knew well the secrets of producing blue colors. Among the monuments of Shahizin, there is a type of tile made by adding white sand, feldspar, and partially ganch to faience - clay. Produced in abundance by the potters of Faenza, Italy, this type of glaze was widely used as household and building materials. The ceramic tiles produced in Metlach, Germany are typed on the floor and called metlach tiles. Faiencebased ceramics were produced as early as Ancient Egypt. Beruni testifies to the fact that Chinese porcelain has been known for a very long time. Ceramics (from the Greek word keramos - clay), porcelain - porcelain (China) made on the basis of a mixture mined in special white clay deposits. Kaolin (the name of one of the mines in China) clay (which is also available near Angren in Uzbekistan) has the ability to bake clear, thin, water-resistant porcelain with images of various colors. Along with the development of pottery and porcelain production, architectural tiles also improved. By the 15th century, the main direction of coating various tile elements in majolica and mosaic methods appeared in architecture. The decoration of wall surfaces and architectural forms (domes, column heads, surfaces, arches, bagals, muqarnas, sharafa, etc.) reached a high level in the architecture of the Timurid era [6]: Me'morchilik va qurilish muammolari 2024 йил, №2 сон 14 1. Cast glazes on carved terracotta - a ceramic plate with a carved pattern, a variety of ceramic architectural forms (concave, relief, circular, arcuate surfaces, muqarnas pieces, among them). This method, where the colors are the same or several colors are given separately, has been known since the 12th century. It was highly developed in the 14th century; 2. The width of Islamic, girih, epigraphic flowers is 1.5-2 mm. thin elements are also created up to the thickness. Carved terracotta (ceramic) architectural elements given a completely different color glaze; 3. Majolica tiles, a method of covering the ceramic surface with tiles in different colors. These boards are baked on a ceramic or faience base and then patterned. Since the glaze is given in different compositions, the colors are baked separately. Although such majolica was prepared by Eastern and Western masters in different ways, it was only during the Timurid period that it was widely used to cover large surfaces on the exterior of buildings; 4. The production of majolica tiles with relief, carving or embossed color separation (that is, they do not flow into each other) is observed in the constructions of the Timurid period; 5. During this period, gold plating on majolica patterns was also practiced; 6. Brick glaze mosaics - the art of making mosaics from glaze bricks given one type of color. The further development of this method led to koshinburush; 7. Although the art of mosaic covering from cut tile began in the Middle East, Iran, it was not as prominently displayed in architectural

decoration as in the period of Timurid architecture in terms of covering large surfaces, fineness, clarity of colors, and skill of dialing. Some experts associate the method of glazing thin tiles and then cutting them to make a mosaic with the practice of craftsmen from the city of Koshan, Iran. However, during this period, the art of tiling was at a high level in Movarounnahr. Koshinburush - the method of cutting, cutting, and sawing flower and pattern lines from tile boards to cover the Shahizinda complex in Samarkand, Tuman Aqo's mausoleum (1405), was the peak of the development of this method. It is surprising that even very delicate flower paths are cut. Although the cut tile mosaic method requires a lot of work, the colors are clear, clear, and have a high artistic effect when they are selected with jeweler's precision; 8. The skill of using various techniques, such as brick glaze mosaic, glaze majolica, carved brick, ganch, wood carvings, and the harmony of the tiling method, skillfully used in the external decoration of buildings, reached a high level in the architecture of this period, and determined the stages of the development of architectural decoration in the following centuries. During the 16th-18th centuries, in the architecture of Khorezm, Bukhara, Shahrisabz, Kokand, Samarkand, various methods of architectural porcelain continued to be used. In Kok, brick-glazed mosaic, in Samarkand, majolica, koshinbrush methods, and in Khorezm, the use of majolica continued successfully. The famous madrasas of Samarkand in Registan Square, Sherdor, Tillakori madrasas, many buildings in Khiva, Kokan Horde, many buildings in Bukhara are evidence of this process; 9. Many years of research are being carried out in order to restore and repair architectural ceramic tiles. Especially with ceramics, although there are tests and experiments to find the ancient quality of paints and glazes, to restore the original colors, and to determine the methods of replacing the coatings, the originality of the repaired architectural ceramic coatings remains a problem. Violation of technologies is observed during tile baking, color preparation, and installation; 10. The main reasons: it is necessary to prepare this raw material in the same quality as the old potters and tilers. The choice and method of fuel for cooking tiles in Khumdots can also be appropriate if it is done in ancient technology. Each type of tile requires its own preparation. Installation in place, i.e. coverings in the ancient way, khataba - cavity, using compounds for gluing to the surface in accordance with the experience of folk masters, makes the practice of modern repair science effective.

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